

How it helps farmers:

Contact Us:

www.dairy40.eu

info@dairy40.eu

Follow us on social media!

@dAlry40

Improved animal health:

Continuous monitoring enables early disease detection.

Optimised milking and feeding:

AI-driven adjustments for efficiency and cow well-being.

Higher Milk Quality:

Real-time analysis ensures premium milk quality.

Sustainability impact:

- 25% reduction in carbon footprint per kg of milk
- 30% decrease in cow sickness days
- Efficient use of resources

CyRIC

UAB
Universitat Autònoma
de Barcelona

ALPES
LASERS

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Education and Research EAER
State Secretariat for Education,
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dairy_{4.0}

Advanced, trustworthy
AI and data solutions
for individualised
automated milking &
feeding of dairy cows

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What we're developing:

Animal Health Monitoring:

Utilising advanced cameras and sensors, **dAlry 4.0** monitors vital signs, body condition, udder health, and animal characteristics to ensure early detection of health issues.

Individualised Milking

& Feeding:

Customised milking settings and feeding programs respond to each cow's needs, improving efficiency and comfort.

Milk Quality Analysis:

A novel sensor technology provides rapid, on-site milk quality assessments, ensuring optimal processing and storage.

Smart Data Integration:

A cloud-based platform processes real-time data, supporting informed decisions for better farm management.

Integration with existing farm systems:

dAlry 4.0 will be integrated with automated milking robots and farm management platforms, ensuring easy adoption with minimal disruptions to farming operations.

Cutting-edge AI tools

- **Multimodal learning for animal health monitoring**, leverages advanced AI models that integrate multiple data sources
- **Self-supervised learning & data augmentation**, enhance AI adaptability by improving performance with minimal human input
- **Explainable AI for system transparency**, ensures farmers can understand and trust AI-driven decisions.
- **Farmer-in-the-loop system building**, combines AI insights with farmer expertise to improve decision-making